

Paper Chromatographic Studies of Some Cations with Solvents Containing N, N-Dimethylformamide (DMF)[†]

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N, N-Dimethylformamide (DMF) and mixtures containing DMF with many non-aqueous solvents have been tested as possible solvent systems for the separation of Pb,⁺⁺Ag,⁺Hg,⁺⁺ and Tl⁺⁺ ions on discs and strips of Whatman No. 1 and 3 mm chromatographic papers. Rf values for these ions have been reported in about 56 solvent systems which include pure, binary and ternary mixtures each containing DMF. Separation of different combinations of these ions have been achieved successfully in some of these mixed solvent systems.

REGARDING the suitability of a solvent system, no theoretical predictions can be made strictly.

But from the perusal of the literature it is seen that in the field of inorganic paper chromatography, the solvents generally used so far are either those with high polarity such as alcohols, ketones, ethers and esters; or those which possess complex forming tendency such as acetylacetone, acetoacetic ester etc. Besides these, few recent papers describe the systematic investigation of less polar solvents like chloroform¹⁻³ for the inorganic paper chromatography and emphasize the utility of mixed systems.

N,N-Dimethylformamide is one such solvent, which incorporates both the above properties in it i.e., high polarity (dielectric constant = 36.7 at 25°) and tendency to form complexes^{4,4-a} with metallic ions. Therefore it is expected to prove a good fundamental solvent for the paper chromatography of inorganics.

So far this solvent has been used mostly as stationary phase in the chromatography of organic compounds by few workers^{5,6}; Baeyer *et al.*⁷ have used DMF, mixed with *n*-butanol and water (1:9:10) as mobile phase for the separation of aliphatic aldehydes. This has also been used in TLC of organic compounds⁸⁻¹⁰. The use of DMF as mobile phase for inorganic paper chromatography has been virtually neglected and hence needs systematic investigation. The present studies therefore have been carried out with the view of using DMF (pure and mixed) for paper chromatography of the cations of the first group of analytical chart i.e. Pb,⁺⁺ Ag,⁺ Hg,⁺⁺ and Tl⁺⁺ which have been separated previously by Bhatnagar and Sharma² in mixed solvents containing chloroform.

Experimental

(a) Apparatus, Paper and Reagents :

For the radial development of the chromatogram,

circular chromatographic troughs (20x20x50 cm) and for ascending and descending developments, cylindrical gas jars (12 cm diam. x 35 cm height) with usual accessories were used. Whatman No. 1 filter paper was used throughout for Rf measurements, and separations were done on No. 1 as well as 2 mm chromatographic paper.

Solutions of Lead(II), Silver(I), Mercury(II) and Thallium(I) ions were prepared from their nitrates (E.Merck & Proanalysis quality). The concentrations of cations for Rf measurements were 5 to 10 µg per 100 ml and for separation purpose 20 µg per 100 ml.

DMF was distilled under reduced pressure⁴ and all other solvents were double distilled. All the mixed solvents, each containing DMF were prepared on volume to volume basis except in case of phenol where it was on weight to volume basis. Glacial acetic acid (BDH) was used as such to acidify the solvent system on volume to volume basis. Yellow ammonium sulphide solution was used as spray-reagent to locate the spots.

(b) Procedure :

Rf values of cations were determined on Whatman No. 1 discs (11 cm diameter) by usual Rutter's technique of radial development with the slight modification in spotting the solution. The wick was cut out from the centre tapering towards periphery. The ions were spotted equidistant on a circle around the connecting end of the wick and the chromatogram was obtained as usual. The Rf values were then measured with respect to outer and inner fronts and reported as Rf (o) and Rf (i).

The separations of suitable combinations of the cations were carried out where differences in Rf values permitted to do so. For separations, the mixture of cation solution was spotted at the centre

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of the disc which gave concentric rings for the different cations. The separations were also carried out on the strips.

Results and Discussion

Rf values for cations under study have been summarised in Table 1 (as Rf(o) x 100 and Rf(i) x 100). The solvents have been denoted by English alphabet as A=DMF, B=chloroform, C=Carbon

tetrachloride, D=Phenol, E=*n*-butanol, F=isopropanol, G=acetone, H=methyl ethyl ketone, I=methyl acetate, J=acetic acid (Glacial) and K=nitric acid (16 N).

From the study of Rf values it is clear that most of the ions do not migrate in less polar or non-polar pure solvents like-chloroform¹¹ isopropanol and carbontetrachloride. In pure DMF, all the ions move upto sufficient distances. Lederer¹², Pollard

TABLE 1—RF VALUES OF CATIONS X 100

S. No.	Solvent System	Composition	Ag ⁺ Rf(o)-Rf(i)	Pb ⁺⁺ (o)-(i)	Hg ⁺⁺ (o)-(i)	Tl ⁺ (o)-(i)
1.	A	Pure	50-32	72-50	99-86	60-42
2.	B	Pure	d	d	d	d
3.	A:B	1:1	22-d	75-69	100-83	52-d
4.	A:B	1:2	24-d	76-69	92-76	56-d
5.	A:B	1:3	22-d	78-72	97-88	63-43
6.	A:B:J	1:1:2%	00-00	78-82	100-74	66-41
7.	A:B:J	1:2:2%	00-00	93-73	97-83	50-d
8.	A:B:J	1:3:2%	00-00	45-31	92-83	33-17
9.	C	Pure	d	d	d	d
10.	A:C	1:1	41-d	63-d	93-81	61-d
11.	A:C	1:2	45-d	78-62	96-76	47-d
12.	A:C	1:3	68-50	80-68	100-72	65-45
13.	A:C:J	1:1:2%	60-41	69-T	100-90	68-31
14.	A:C:J	1:2:2%	52-d	72-34	96-64	43-d
15.	A:C:J	1:3:2%	62-41	85-70	100-79	60-32
16.	A:D	5%(w/v)	56-37	75-68	100-57	50-25
17.	A:D	10%(w/v)	46-d	62-55	100-84	48-d
18.	A:D	15%(w/v)	36-d	62-44	84-44	27-d
19.	A:D:J	5%:2%	45-d	67-60	84-85	41-d
20.	A:D:J	10%:2%	56-d	93-90	100-86	50-37
21.	A:D:J	15%:2%	50-d	93-89	100-83	55-44
22.	E	Pure	00-00	83-61 T	91-82	65-20
23.	A:E	1:1	28-d	73-44	100-93	37-d
24.	A:E	1:2	00-00	46-d	93-83	26-15
25.	A:E	1:3	00-00	64-47	100-95	93-68
26.	A:E:J	1:1:2%	00-00	57-42	100-94	46-d
27.	A:E:J	1:2:2%	11-d	44-34	97-90	19-13
28.	A:E:J	1:3:2%	00-00	63-25	100-93	79-62
29.	F	Pure	00-00	d	100-95 T	00-00
30.	A:F	1:1	00-00	d	100-91	21-d
31.	A:F	1:2	00-00	40-d	90-80	24-d
32.	A:F	1:3	00-00	69-52	100-87	50-d
33.	A:F:J	1:1:2%	00-00	56-d	97-91	29-d
34.	A:F:J	1:2:2%	00-00	39-d	88-79	13-d
35.	A:F:J	1:3:2%	00-00	81-78 M	100-80	37-d
36.	G	Pure	73-d	40-d	100-78	60-13
37.	A:G	1:1	50-d	83-75	92-78	50-d
38.	A:G	1:2	50-d	74-71	94-73	52-d
39.	A:G	1:3	34-d	79-71	100-81	52-24
40.	A:G:J	1:1:2%	55-d	74-44	100-94	50-25
41.	A:G:J	1:2:2%	62-41	76-69	100-78	50-14
42.	A:G:J	1:3:2%	64-48	88-76	100-85	63-17
43.	H	Pure	78-d	76-69	100-86	87-66
44.	A:H	1:1	52-d	83-75	100-86	52-43
45.	A:H	1:2	44-38 M	41-37	84-72	37-d
46.	A:H	1:3	36-d	76-60	94-76	48-12
47.	A:H:J	1:1:2%	58-45	83-79	100-76	47-d
48.	A:H:J	1:2:2%	70-40	79-76	100-85	50-d
49.	A:H:J	1:3:2%	64-45	84-74	100-78	60-30
50.	A:I	1:1	64-40	50-30	31-08	69-19
51.	A:I	1:2	74-35	80-67	80-60	76-64
52.	A:I	1:3	96-75	93-74	87-69	92-71
53.	A:I:J	1:1:2%	96-76	85-70	82-68	85-63
54.	A:I:J	1:2:2%	93-78	87-73	84-68	100-73
55.	A:I:J	1:3:2%	91-74	90-71	85-65	72-76
56.	A:E:K	3:1:2%	64-50	87-81	100-86	36-07

d = diffusion, T = tailing, M = multiple spotting.

*et al.*¹³ and Haraswa¹⁴ have shown the need of solvents either with high but different polarity (usually highly polar solvents) or with complexing property, for effective separation of inorganic ions. DMF possesses both these characteristics in it i.e. high polarity and complex forming property. The results of present study indicate that the high Rf values in pure DMF may be due to its high polarity. In mixed solvents some regularities have been observed. The Rf values in mixed solvents increase in general with the increasing ratio of chloroform, carbontetrachloride and isopropanol which is not in accordance with the expectations and previous findings¹¹. Hence it may be concluded that in mixed systems polarity alone may not be the only factor effecting migration. The deviation in values from expected should be due to the solvating effect of the solvent on the adduct⁴ formed between metal ion and DMF. The decreasing Rf values with increasing concentration of phenol in DMF are in the order of decreasing basic character of the system. Systems containing *n*-butanol have been largely employed successfully in chromatography. In the present study also it proved a good system with DMF. Presence of mineral acid gives still better results and compact rings in this system as tested for one system No. 56 (Table 1) only.

Separations achieved in different combinations of cations are tabulated in Table 2. Binary separations are possible many in number and have not been mentioned; only ternary and quaternary separations are tabulated. Separations of cations in solvents without acid (proton) conform to the mechanism as proposed by Bhatnagar and Bhatnagar¹⁵ on impregnated papers.

TABLE 2—SEPARATIONS ACHIEVED

S.No.	Ions separated	Solvent system No.
1.	Ag, ⁺ Tl, ⁺ Hg ⁺⁺	24
2.	Ag, ⁺ Pb, ⁺⁺ Hg ⁺⁺	25
3.	Pb, ⁺⁺ Hg, ⁺⁺ Tl ⁺	27
4.	Ag, ⁺ Pb ⁺⁺ , Hg, ⁺⁺ Tl ⁺	28
5.	Ag, ⁺ Pb, ⁺⁺ , Hg, ⁺⁺ Tl ⁺	6
6.	All the four ions	31
7.	All the four ions	46
8.	All the four ions	49

Time of run of the chromatogram ranges from 3 to 3.30 Hours at 32-34°.

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